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RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: NAMUYABA

FIRST NAME: PHEONA

PROGRAM CODE: DME

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 93%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-12)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
6. CMS Crib sheet (EUCLID 2021, 43-56)
7. Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2021, 58-62)

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INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1) SUMMARY

This is an exciting journey for me, although worried about the pressure that comes with pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.). I am very committed, and the program is self-paced, I will endeavor to plan and balance my doctoral study, work, and family responsibilities.

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I have reviewed the ACA-401D coursework pack, reviewed the document on How to Write a Response Paper (RP), and watched the tutorial video, which were instrumental in setting a good foundation not just for my first response paper but the entire doctoral program. They focus on providing students with writing basics of international academic and professional papers. The document on How to Write a Response Paper (RP) guides the student on how to structure a response paper, important points when writing a response paper. It provides some valuable examples of response papers (EUCLID 2021). Furthermore, the basic tutorial video directed by Prof Laurent offers a step-by-step guide to format, customize and use the response paper template (Cleenewerck 2021).

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Chapter one of the ACA-401D coursework pack gives a general overview of basic essay writing, the steps of writing a good essay, and some rules of thumb for writing a paper. Chapter two helps students understand and use punctuation marks, offers practical examples of [punctuation marks, and](#) distinguishes between correct and incorrect punctuation. Chapter three helps students understand and differentiate between US and UK English, while chapter four focuses on [plagiarism](#) and how to avoid it. Chapter four further explains how and when to cite and paraphrase and teaches students how to insert footnotes using MS Word. Chapter five helps students appreciate a style guide and its relevance in writing, while chapter six helps students understand the Chicago style and specifications in writing. Lastly, chapter seven focused on Latin abbreviations and expressions. The document is very relevant in equipping new students like me with the knowledge and skills [to write](#) academic and professional papers.

2) REACTION TO THE BOOK

a) Essay writing

Cleenewerck and Gulma explained that academic writing is nonfictional but seeks to provide the answer(s) to hypotheses that are evidence-based. Although writing an essay can be an iterative process, the book outlines some basic steps which make essay writing a seamless process. The steps include; early start-up, defining the question and analyzing the task, and drafting an initial plan ([EUCLID, 2021, 7](#)). Starting early gives the writer adequate time to plan, collect information, write, arrange/re-align, proofread, and submit the essay on time. Defining the question, analyzing the task, and drawing an initial plan help the writer understand the required information and plan where to get [it](#) and how to align it in the essay. This approach will be helpful to me as I embark on my academic writing. I plan to revisit and review my draft after a few days with a fresh mind which will enable me to not only clear the spelling and grammar errors but ensure there is logical flow in the document.

Cleenewerck and Gulma further explain that after understanding the research topic, the writer needs to read and research because that will give knowledge and evidence to develop the thesis and answers (7). As I write my doctoral essays, I will ensure to highlight and mark key aspects from my reading so that I can come back to them when writing and referencing. Cleenewerck & Gulma also share the structure of the essay (that includes introduction, body and conclusion) and some effective writing tips that I will definitely employ in my doctoral journey.

Lastly, this section of the document highlights the rules of thumb that are critical for a doctoral student to develop a good academic and professional paper. They include; stating the main thesis of the paper at (or near) the beginning, staying focused, not leading with such sweeping generalities, writing clearly, not making the writing boring and clumsy, supporting assertions, taking the views I discuss seriously, and not plagiarizing other peoples' work ([EUCLID, 2021, 7](#)).

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b) Punctuation marks

Accurate punctuation adds simplicity and correctness to our work. I need to use minimal punctuation if I want to retain the sentence's meaning. Cleenewerck and Gulma demonstrate how and when to use the apostrophe, brackets, bullet points, colon and semicolon, commas, defining Vs non defining information, dashes and hyphens, ellipsis, full stops, exclamation marks, question marks, quotation marks, and using other punctuation with quotation marks (16-23). I find it interesting to differentiate when to use the colon and semicolon. I have used both before, but wrongly, the document provides useful examples that help me appreciate which situations I can apply the two.

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c) American Vs British English

Both American and British English have a lot in common, and they are different dialects of World English. Cleenewerck and Gulma illustrate the differences between American and British English, sharing some practical examples to help the student appreciate the difference and application in daily life. The differences range from spelling, pronunciation, grammar, punctuation, usage of large collective nouns and pluralized adjectives, terms of expression, and creativity, (24-33). In my view, it is fine to use any version of English as long as the writer is clear about which version s/he is using and ensures consistency throughout the writing. I also note that some academic writing prefers one English Version to the other for various reasons.

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d) Plagiarism

Chapter four explains the concept of plagiarism and guides students on how to avoid it, how/when to cite and paraphrase, and be able to insert footnotes using MS Word. I will try to avoid plagiarism in all my academic writing. This is possible by correctly citing and referencing content from other sources indicating authors and page numbers. Cleenewerck and Gulma further differentiate when to cite and when not to cite, how to make in-text citing and listing of works cited, and how to write short and short and long quotations. I have learned from Cleenewerck and Gulma that “too much quotations make the paper look like it’s not yours and encourages us to limit quotation to situations when the strong language in the quote emphasizes the meaning very well and when the student needs to quote the authority figures to persuade the reader” (36). I have learned that I only need to make citations when independently writing papers, not during supervised exams: I struggled to comprehend how a student must cram the authors and page numbers to cite them in supervised exams.

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e) Style guide

Cleenewerck and Gulma explains what a style is, why a writer needs a style guide, and what a style guide constitutes. The authors point out that “Style is much more than just the correct usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary. Style encompasses different

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aspects like preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK v US, for example), readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, and the use of symbols.” I notice this is one mistake we have always made at my organization, where we hire consultants to carry out assessments or document case stories, but we do not guide them on the organization's style. We have ended up with products below the standard that require a lot of time to review and refine.

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f) Chicago style and specification

This chapter explains what the Chicago style is and gives practical examples of how to use the Chicago style. Cleenewerck and Gulma elaborate on: Chicago style and usage that, includes how to use abbreviations and acronyms, capitalization and compound words, emphasis (Italics and Quotes), numbers and dates, and quotations: Chicago page formatting that includes; title and text page, footnotes, headings and lists, bibliography and tables, and table notes; Chicago endnotes/footnotes including; authors and books, journals and newspapers, reports and papers, references and documents, and Chicago bibliographies (44-57). What I learn is the need to be consistent in using the style and specification, and as a student, mastery comes with practice. I will continuously practice this style throughout my doctoral program, and my writing will improve gradually.

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g) Latin abbreviations and expressions

Chapter Seven focuses on improving the student’s understanding of the common Latin abbreviations used in writing, the meaning of Latin abbreviations used in writing, and the meaning of common Latin expressions (EUCLID, 2021, 58-64). I noticed I have used most of the abbreviations wrongly and didn’t even know the meaning of some of them. The Period-1 course pack will not only help me learn how to write my first response paper, Still, it will be my reference document throughout my doctoral program and current work to ensure my writing is professional and complies with the expected standards.

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3) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the ACA-401D coursework pack has been a great eye-opener and a good foundation as I embark on my doctoral journey. The ACA-401D coursework pack and basic Tutorial have not just introduced me to writing my first response letter but helped me appreciate the basics of writing good essays, punctuation, abbreviations, and plagiarism, among others, which I will employ throughout my doctoral program and professional work.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

EUCLID. 2021. *How to Write a Response Paper (RP)*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. 2021. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Euclid University. <https://vimeo.com/157480457>

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.